

Development of E-Learning Technology in Designing and Making E-book-Based Learning Modules in Audio Video Engineering Subjects to Increase Student Learning Creativity

*¹Diena Rahma Adila, ²Basori, ³Febri Liantoni

¹Informatics and Computer Engineering Education Teacher Training and Education Faculty, Sebelas Maret University

^{2,3}Informatics and Computer Engineering Education Teacher Training and Education Faculty, Sebelas Maret University

Corresponding Email : Dienaadila447@gmail.com

Abstract:

E-book learning media is very necessary at this time because it has the advantage of being more interactive and efficient, it can also create teaching and learning activities that are more effective compared to printed books. With problems with the learning system implemented at SMK Negeri Kartoharjo, they still use package books, making students feel bored. The purpose of this study (1) to find out how to design e-book-based learning modules in TAV subjects to increase student creativity, (2) to find out how to make learning modules in the development of e-learning technology in the form of e-books on TAV subjects to enhance students' learning creativity. This research is research and development. The data collection techniques used are observation, questionnaire, literature, type of data. The subjects involved consisted of 1 media expert, 1 material expert, and 56 learners. The resulting data is in the form of quantitative data and qualitative data. The results of the due diligence by material experts obtained 90% in the category of very feasible, and by media experts obtained 89.75% in the category of very feasible, for the small group test gained 89% in the very decent category. It can be concluded that the media in the form of ZmarTAV digital books is included in the category of very worthy to be used as a learning medium for audio and video processing techniques in video editing materials using video processing software

Keywords: *Audio Video Engineering, E-Book, Learning Module*

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Introduction

. The development of technology in an effort to improve the quality of education greatly affects the quality and character of students to create good graduates. In today's era, advances in informatics technology, especially in the field of multimedia, have developed rapidly and have a positive influence on the world of education. In Law article 1 No. 20 of 2003 against the National Education System, education is a planned conscious effort in order to create a learning atmosphere and learning process so that students are actively developing their potential and have religious spiritual power, self-control, personality, intelligence, noble character, as well as necessary skills of himself, society, nation and state.

Development of learning media can help students be active and motivated during learning. Based on the use of existing facilities in schools, it can be a support in the development of learning used by computer-based educators. In conducting learning, you can also take advantage of technology in the form of information in the form of e-learning. E-learning is needed not only by competent educators but by utilizing technology in making teaching materials in making learning media effective. E-learning technology makes it easy for every learner to learn as well as recall their lessons according to (Kosasi, 2015).

E-learning is a form of learning model that is facilitated and supported by the use of information and communication technology. In applying information and communication technology, teachers can influence the learning process that makes it easier for students to learn. It can be said to be effective in the learning process if it can utilize information and communication technology appropriately (Hanum, 2013).

This very significant change is already taking place in everyday life, moreover, the most important change that occurs is in the field of education. The quality of education in Indonesia is relatively low compared to other countries. Various kinds of technological advances have begun to be applied in the world of education, such as to support more efficient learning, such as the use of technology for distance learning, and so on. Where in the field of education has a big influence with the existence of 21st century learning (Journal of Education, 2021). 21st century skills are about producing a generation that has character and has certain competencies.

Changes in this era cannot be avoided by anyone so that adequate human resources (HR) are needed to be ready to adjust and be able to compete on a global scale (Lase, 2019). Citing the 2015 World Economic Forum report, the skill strategies needed by students for the 21st century are as follows: Critical Thinking, Creativity, Curiosity, Communication, initiative, adaptability, Collaboration, persistence & fortitude, Social awareness & culture, Leadership.

Shows that towards the 21st century students no longer just need traditional academic learning. Rather, it is education that offers learning services that are up-to-date in collaboration, communication and problem solving, critical thinking, creative and innovative. This ability or skill no longer only relies on face-to-face learning but a combination of online learning (e-learning) and face-to-face (face to face) or can also be called a blended learning model by combining face-to-face learning with distance learning. Therefore, the creativity skills of learning from students are expected to help students solve one of these problems (KIBASP, 2021)

Creativity is an expression (expression) and uniqueness of the individual in interaction with his environment (astri Damayanti, maman surahman, sugiman, 2019). Creativity reflects divergent thinkers i.e. abilities that can provide a wide variety of alternative answers. Creativity can be used to predict learning success. But actually everyone is creative. To get such a person, it is necessary to have training and guidance from parents or teachers. It is also undeniable that the teacher's creativity in teaching sometimes also affects the interest in learning in the student's own class (Tinton Tri Pebrianto, M. Tauchid Noor, Supriyanto, 2015). Each student has different abilities, to develop them students are expected to have high creativity (Richard, Firosalia, Indri, 2019). In independence, a person must have a creative attitude and be able to develop ideas or ideas that are constructive in nature according to (Isnawati & Samian, 2015). According to (Effendi, 2016) Operationally creativity can be formulated as an ability that reflects fluency, flexibility (flexibility), and originality in thinking, as well as the ability to elaborate (develop, enrich, detail) an idea.

The main objective of learning activities is to obtain maximum learning outcomes. The focus in Indonesia is in improving student learning creativity (Novianto et al., 2018). Discourse improves the quality of learning, which is an important part of creativity which can now be well received in the learning process and learning outcomes. So that the education system in Indonesia is still making improvements to improve student learning achievement (Rezni Surya Ningrum, et al., 2018). But nowadays teachers still use a lot of conventional learning models. Students tend to feel bored when following the learning process, there are

mistakes in choosing the use of inappropriate learning methods. In a teaching and learning process, learning media has a very important role because one of its main functions is learning media as a teaching aid that also affects the climate, conditions and learning environment that is arranged and created by educators (Rizky Kurniawan Rangkuti, et al., 2019).

One of the learning methods used is the use of E-book media. E-book stands for Electronic book is a type of electronic book in the form of softcopy that can be read through electronic devices such as computers, smartphones and mobile phones according to (Gaol et al., 2019). E-Books have the advantage of being more interactive and efficient than printed books. The way e-books are distributed and delivered to users is also very easy. Explanations equipped with repeatable video tutorials make E-Books easier to understand than printed books. The appearance and font that can be changed as desired also includes the advantages of E-Book to attract more students' interest compared to printed books. In addition, E-Books can also be given an evaluation test whose results can be seen directly. From that statement, the author chose to develop a learning media in the form of a digital book that includes material both written and images and also for students and teachers in order to create more effective teaching and learning activities. That way the researcher conducted a survey activity at one of the Vocational High Schools located in Kartoharjo. The thing that researchers find in the existing problems is in the learning process using package books, so that students feel bored because the teacher explains in lectures and repeatedly.

The purpose of this research is to find out how to design e-book-based learning modules on TAV subjects and also to find out how to make learning modules in the development of e-learning technology in the form of e-books on TAV subjects to increase student creativity

Research Method

This research uses methods (Research and Development). Where metode research and development is a method used to produce a particular product and test the effectiveness of the product. Menurut (Borg & Gall, 1984) research and development education is a process used for the development and validation of research products. The products referred to by Borg & Gall do not only include material objects, such as textbooks, educational films, and so on. According to Nana (2009: 165) the steps in the research and development process show a cycle, starting with the existence of needs and problems that require solving using a certain product. In the research and development method using the development model developed by Gall and Borg in Nana (2009: 163). Where in this study only meets 5 aspects, due to limited time, energy, and costs to conduct research with the research and development method from Borg and Gall in full.

The subjects involved consisted of 1 media expert, namely a lecturer in the Informatics and Computer Engineering Education study program who has experts in the field of multimedia, 1 material expert, namely a Multimedia teacher at SMK Negeri Kartoharjo with qualifications in the field of multimedia, and 56 Multimedia students at SMK Negeri Kartoharjo.

The observasi method uses direct observation through the object to be studied to collect information related to the type of media that is suitable for the delivery of TAV material at SMK Negeri Kartoharjo. The questionnaire gives questions to respondents and then takes data to determine eligibility. The literature or literature method, which is to collect several sources of information that is relevant and in accordance with the problem under study, can be sourced from scientific books, scientific reports, scientific essays, books, and dissertations. The type of data taken is the type of authenticative K data taken from the media feasibility assessment while the kualitatif is obtained from the results of observations, literature studies and also suggestions for improvement.

Researchers take a Likert scale to conduct testing, the assessment sheet will be validated by a team of experts before finally the questionnaire is distributed to respondents, with assessments: Strongly Agree (SS), Agree (S), Disagree (KS), Disagree (TS) and Very Very Less (SK). The assessment sheet was obtained through data collection and modification from the Adhi research sheet (2019). And on each questionnaire is worth 1- 5. It can be seen in Table1.

Table 1. Likert Score Criteria

Shoes	Criterion
5	Very Agree
4	Agree
3	Less Agree
2	Disagree
1	Very Disagree

In making it easier for readers, the resulting score will be calculated through the following formula:

$$\text{Persentase (\%)} = \frac{F}{B} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

F is the result of the assessment and B is the maximum value of the assessment (Riduwan, 2013) Then a classification will be carried out against the values can be seen in the table (2)

Table 2. Percentage of Learning Media Eligibility Criteria

Assessment Criteria	Percentage
Very Decent	81% - 100%
Proper	61% - 80%
Less Viable	41% - 60%
Not Worth It	21% - 40%
Very Unworthy	0% - 20%

(Source : Riduwan, 2013)

Result and Analysis

This research aims to produce learning media in the form of Desktop-based ZmarTAV digital books. The results of the literature study for the vocational high school level multimedia expertise with Adobe Premiere Pro material that will be studied are how to operate and also create video projects in the Adobe Premiere Pro application. As for the process of making learning media, it must be adjusted to the age characteristics of SMK students, where the age of the student has a modern spirit and always follows technological developments. By making interactive learning media and following technological developments in this day and age, it can certainly attract the attention of students as well as students do not feel bored and are very efficient if students want to study at school or outside of school. Tutorial video is a good breakthrough for SMK students because it is a learning medium that has the advantage of being able to be repeated according to student wishes and can make it easier for educators to deliver practical tutorials more easily. There are three stages for making learning media, namely planning, making and testing.

The planning stage is divided into three, namely making teaching materials where the first step is in making the material to be taught in the e-book with modernization in accordance with the times. Then the next step is to make a navigation design or navigation structure, which in this study uses a linear navigation design that is made as a reference in making buttons in the media that has been designed. In the next planning stage, the storyboard is made as a reference to put components on the learning media.

The stage of making or developing product drafts, at this stage, development of the media is carried out by making learning media in accordance with the initial planning in accordance with the teaching material guided by the syllabus. This stage is up to the functional trial of the product where a trial is carried out to test all the components of each on learning media. And after the functional test of the product is completed and declared as a whole valid, it can be tested for feasibility by media experts and material experts.

The testing phase on the e-book is carried out by media experts and material experts by filling out the application feasibility questionnaire and media experts providing suggestions for improvements for the media. As for the percentage of eligibility by material experts can be seen in table 3.

Table 3. Material expert

Aspects	Percentage
Accuracy	18/20x100% = 90%
Completeness	9/10x100% = 90%
Interest/Attention	14/15x100% = 93%
Conformity	9/10x100% = 90%
Benefits	14/15x100% = 93%
Motivation	9/10x100% = 90%
Flexibility	17/20x100% = 85%
Average	90%

Then the results of the percentage of eligibility calculations by media experts can be seen in table 4.

Table 4. Media experts

Aspects	Percentage
Functionality	21/25x100% = 84%
Readability	20/20x100% = 100%
Facilities	30/35x100% = 86%
Display	31/35x100% = 89%
Average	89,75 %
Aspects	Percentage

The results of the feasibility test by material experts were 90% in the "Very Feasible" category, and the feasibility results by media experts obtained 89.75% in the "Very Feasible" category, also the trials in small groups obtained a percentage of 89% in the "Very Feasible" category. So the conclusion that the media in the form of ZmarTAV digital books is included in the category of very worthy to be used as a learning medium for audio and video processing techniques in video editing materials using video processing software

. It is known based on the results of the discussion that the media in the form of ZmarTAV digital books is included in the category of very worthy of being used as a learning medium for audio and video processing techniques in video editing materials using video processing software. To find out the feasibility of ZmarTAV media, data collection was carried out using a questionnaire to respondents, namely material experts, media experts and users. The feasibility of material from ZmarTAV media can be assessed from several aspects, including material accuracy, completeness of material, interest/attention, material suitability, motivation and material flexibility. From the aspect of interest / attention and usefulness, the same percentage result was 93%, where the percentage result was in the very feasible category. The material flexibility aspect obtained a percentage result of 85%, where the percentage result was in the very feasible category. The average of the overall aspects of material feasibility assessment is 90%. So it can be concluded that on average from the results of this percentage, ZmarTAV digital book media is included in the category group that is very worthy of being used as a learning medium.

The ZmarTAV media feasibility test can be assessed from several aspects, namely the functionality aspect of obtaining a percentage result of 84%, where the results are classified as very feasible. Then from the aspect of readability obtained a percentage result of 100%, where the percentage result is included in the very feasible category. Aspect of ease of obtaining a percentage result of 86%, where the result belongs to the category of very feasible. And from the aspect of display, it obtained a result of 89%, where the result is also included in the very decent category. The average of all the percentage results is 89.75%, so it can be concluded that the ZmarTAV application media is very feasible if it is used as a learning medium.

Trials in this small group of aspects tested include aspects of the material, video tutorials, and appearance. And in this test, it was tested on 56 students at SMK N 1 Kartoharjo. Before trying the ZmarTAV application media, students are given directions on how to operate the digital book. Then after finishing trying to perform the operation of the digital book, students can fill out the questionnaire. At the time of the trial, the results of the interview with students said that this digital book is very interesting and good for attracting students' attention, also that this digital book looks less boring for learning media than learning using textbooks. Students also say that this digital book is easy to understand and how to use it is very easy. From the calculation of the percentage of material aspects, the result was 88%, where the result was in the category of very feasible. A video tutorial spec obtained a percentage result of 87% belonging to the very decent category. And in the aspect of display obtained a percentage result of 90%, hasil percentage belongs to the category is very feasible. So from these three aspects, the average obtained from a percentage of 89% so that it can be concluded that the ZmarTAV application media is very worthy of being used as a learning medium for students.

In addition, based on the results of the questionnaire, it is known that the ZmarTAV application has several advantages and disadvantages that still need improvement. The ZmarTAV application has the advantage that video tutorials can be made by adjusting the material and needs of the user so that the content in the tutorial video is very complete and easy to understand and develop by students. The video tutorial has a very clear sound and also has an image with a very good resolution so that users can easily capture the content of the material. The ZmarTAV application is also equipped with a written tutorial accompanied by images intended so that users can easily capture the steps of the tutorial presented in the form of a video. Quizzes and competency tests placed at the end of the material are one of the advantages in the ZmarTAV application. Quizzes by matching questions to the correct answers are an excellent solution where students can refresh their minds after learning the material that is made interesting. In addition to the advantages that have been mentioned, ZmarTAV also has the advantage of being more efficient in learning with the ZmarTAV digital book application, which can make students more interested in learning using the ZmarTAV application. As for the shortcomings in e-book learning media which lies in the

appearance of the theme that seems plain, then in the future the theme must be made even more attractive so that it can be of interest to many users. In this application, there is no animation, which is also a weakness in this digital book because it emphasizes too much efficiency compared to a more interactive display so that it can attract more interest to users. In addition, as for the shortcomings of the appearance and animation, the ZmarTAV application also has material weaknesses and video tutorials are still classified as learning for beginners so that users who already have more abilities in this field cannot get more knowledge so that there is still a need for material development so that more can be learned by all general audiences, both beginners and professionals.

Conclusion

So it can be concluded that after passing several stages and revisions and improvements that the ZmarTAV learning media that has been developed can be used as a support for learning Audio and Video Processing Techniques at SMK N 1 Kartoharjo. Pthere this research is used only to determine the feasibility of learning media. The stages used are: Observation, planning, product draft development, research and data collection. The results of the ZmarTAV feasibility test were conducted by material experts and media experts. The feasibility test of the material expert obtained a percentage result of 90% for the aspects of accuracy, completeness, suitability, and motivation including the category of very feasible. In the aspect of interest / attention and usefulness obtained a percentage result of 93% so it is very feasible. And in the aspect of flexibility, obtaining a percentage of 85% of the results of the feasibility test of material experts is also included in the very feasible category. On average, from the overall feasibility aspects of material experts obtaining a percentage of 90%, it can be concluded from these results that the ZmarTAV application is very worthy of being used as a digital book as a learning medium. Then the results of the feasibility of media experts on the aspect of functionality obtained a percentage result of 84% very feasible categories. The readability aspect of the media feasibility test obtained a percentage result of 100% in the very decent category. In the aspect of ease in the media feasibility test obtaining a percentage result of 86% is also very feasible. And in the aspect of display in the media feasibility test obtained a percentage result of 89% in the very decent category. The average media feasibility test results obtained a percentage of 89.75% and it can be concluded that the ZmarTAV application in the category is very feasible if it is used as a digital book as a student learning medium.

The use of an inquiry-based learning learning model assisted by an open video repository has a higher effectiveness compared to those who do not use an inquiry-based learning model assisted by an open video repository based on students' learning interests. The learning that occurs between the experimental class and the control class has differences. In classes that use an inquiry-based learning model assisted by an open video repository, the interest in learning is higher than in classes that do not use the learning model. This can be proven by the results of the gain test where classes that use an inquiry-based learning model assisted by an open video repository have higher results than classes that do not use it.

The use of an inquiry-based learning learning model assisted by an open video repository has a higher effectiveness compared to those who do not use an inquiry-based learning model assisted by an open video repository based on student learning outcomes. The learning that occurs between the experimental class and the control class has differences. In classes that use an inquiry-based learning model assisted by an open video repository, the interest in learning is higher than in classes that do not use the learning model. This can be proven by the results of the gain test where classes that use an inquiry-based learning model assisted by an open video repository have higher results than classes that do not use it.

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